

The Future Of E-Commerce: Opportunities, Challenges And Research Technology

Anthony Albert S

Dept. of Applied Commerce, Park's College (Autonomous), Tirupur, India. 641606.

E-Mail: antonyalbert0608@research.org

Aravinth R

Dept. of Applied Commerce, Park's College (Autonomous), Tirupur, India. 641606.

E-Mail: aravinthrajavelu@research.org

ABSTRACT--Data innovation has been assuming a fundamental job later on advancement of money related divisions. Nearly expanded utilization of shrewd portable administrations and web as other appropriations direct for business in the online business. To challenge the web based business in the business. To this study predict a few difficulties in a developing economy. Web based business the greater part of the people groups utilizes in the world. Participating organizations effectively assessed most of difficulties presented by the appropriation of e-commerce; the study was directed to decide information on the utilization and advantages of E-commerce. The study discovered that the respondents had elevated level of information on e-commerce. This paper's study indicated that there is no critical connection between the respondents level of information on the utilization and advantages toward online business, is has acquired progressive changes the commercial center web based business is paying route for enormous business advancement in our country.

Keywords: Business, E-commerce, Information Technology, World.

1. INTRODUCTION

Web retailers keep on endeavoring to make better substance and a sensible shopping involvement in advancement like expanded reality. Electronic trade ads

another method for working together has huge chances. It is quick assembling force and turning into a reality in Australia as in different pieces of the world. The take-up of e-trade in Australia anyway is low with just 4% of deals directed through the internet and just 6% of business characterized by the Australian Bureau of statistics as ,web trade dynamic, (Australian Bureau of statics,2000) .While the idea of web based business may never more be viewed as new in idea, a big piece of e-trade that's still moderately new is the utilization of social media as an example, face book, my space, instagram, and Twitter as a route for internet-based organizations to associate legitimately with clients and endeavor to sell items or services. Many organizations have bombed in separating their online tasks. For example, the basic interpretation of a site into an unknown dialect might be a debacle .

Additionally, past the interface factors it is fundamental to examine to what degree different components impact individuals to purchase, or not, through the web. And furthermore, there are individuals who don't purchase through the internet, in view of protection, security and dread of utilizing MasterCard's have been principle factors contrarily impacting people to purchase through the internet E-trade. Could convey a critical advantage to organizations in creating nations by expanding their command over its place in the stockpile chain, in this way improving its market proficiency (Molla and Heeks, 2007) . It could hence be contended that internet business in Australia presently can't seem to have a critical effect in the commercial center however is moving at a fast pace toward that path.

- The Australian Bureau of Statistics recently surveyed 6, 41,000 businesses on the utilization of computers and also the internet, including internet sites and internet e-commerce.
- A better proportion of enormous organizations accesses the web and uses it for business purposes than small and medium size ones.
- 91% of surveyed businesses use the internet for E-mail, 85% for information searches.
- It implies managing the merchandise and services through the electronic.

WHAT IS E-COMMERCE?

E-commerce OR E-trade is purchasing and selling of products and enterprises or the transmitting of assets and over an electronic system, essentially the on-line. On-line business replaces the traditional business method. E-commerce is directing utilizing assortment of utilizations . As an example, e-mail, fax, on the web lists and shopping indexes and shopping baskets, electronic information exchange (EDI), record move convention and web administrations. For the aim of this study e-commerce is taken to mean doing business electronically. (Lindsay P., 2002)

WHY E-COMMERCE?

With the expanding dispersion of ICTs, more explicitly the on-line, the worldwide business network is quickly moving towards business-to business (B2B) web based business. The purchasers increase an inexpensive little bit of leeway then the on-line gives them access to the worldwide market, by which they'll think about costs across locales, discover regardless of whether costs differ by request fracture and get mindfulness about substitute items.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Prof. Dr. Subhash Masanappa Suryawanshi et al discussed, this paper is outcome of a review of varied research studies. This study has been undertaken to investigate the present trends of e-commerce in India & examine the challenges & opportunities of e-commerce in India.

Josephine Nava-Macali MBA., et al. discussed, this study utilized the descriptive correlation research design. The study found out that the

respondents had very high level of knowledge on e-commerce. It also showed that the respondent has positive attitude toward e-commerce since they're convinced of the benefits of e-commerce. Study showed that there is no significant relationship between the respondents' level of information on the utilization and benefits toward e-commerce.

Mr. Amith Vikram MA., et al. discussed, this paper is outcome of a review of varied research studies dispensed on E-commerce. This paper examines different opportunities of e-commerce. It brings out the general view of growth of e-commerce industry in India from 2007 to 2011.

Nitish Nayyar et al. discussed, this paper's theoretical contribution is to clarify how's M-commerce is developing in India and to identify clear contexts and assistant mechanism.

Dr. (Smt.) Rajeshwari M. Shettar et al. discussed, this paper attempts to focus on the different challenges faced by the E-commerce in India, understand the essential growth factors required for E-commerce, describes the thriving of E-business in India and retail E-trade deals in India. The study also found that, E-commerce provides the assorted types of opportunities to the wholesalers, retailers, producers and therefore the People.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

The paper has been composed supported auxiliary information. The auxiliary information were gathered from distributed books, diaries, look into papers, magazines, day by day paper, web and authority measurable archives. The examination is subjective in nature.

4. BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF E-COMMERCE:

The research for this paper was a part of a quest thesis that examined two key elements in e-commerce from a business perspective, specializing in on benefits and challenges factors resulting in success in each area. The examination included a review of Australia's best 500 organizations .

4.1 BENEFITS OF E-COMMERCE:

The take-up of online business is impacted by its capability to create business esteem and by

consciousness of its member of the potential advantages (Salnoske, 1997). A big explanation behind most organization, regardless of size, to require part in business is to extricate some profit by it. Internet business is no extraordinary. This literature is classified in two main categories – Tangible & In tangible benefits.

Benefits	Research/Literature
Tangible Benefits	
Business efficiency	(Fraser et al. Lee 2001; Riggins, 1999).
Transformation of traditional market chain	(Fraser et al. 2000).
Retained and expanded customer base	(Fraser et al.2000; Rahul, Biju and Abraham 2001; Turban, et al, 2000).
Intangible Benefits	
Consumer Loyalty	(Lee 2001; Hoffman et al.1999; Coulson,1999)
Competitive advantage	(Kalakota et al. 1999; Hoffman et al. 1999; Straub, 2000; Kare-silver,1998) 222

Table 1 Benefits of E-commerce

4.2 CHALLENGES OF E-COMMERCE:

To remove profits by web based business, it is significant for organizations to beat the online business inhibitors and difficulties. The literature are classified as – Technological, Managerial and business challenges.

Challenges	Research/Literature
Technological challenges	
Site issues	(Watson et al.1999; Zhang &von Dran 2000; Lee 2001)
Technological issues including costs, software, infrastructure	(Hoffman et al. 1999; Abeyesekera et al.1999; Rahul et al.2001)
Managerial Challenges	
People and organizational issues	(Hoffman et al. 1999; Feeny 2000)
Obtaining senior Management backing	(Feeny 2000)
Business Challenges	
Customer service	(Whinston et al.1997; Alter, 1999; Lee 2001)
Legal issues	(Hoffman et al. 1999; Lawrence et al. 1998; de Souza & von Wiese 2000)

Table 2 Challenges of E-commerce

5. RESEARCH:

A critical extent of the exploration answered to this point concentrated on the retail/discount dispense with minimal detailed work or research on the take-up of on-line business within the banking and money industry. Ongoing Australian research investigated from the purpose of view of Australia's best 500 organizations the three key territories of web based business benefits, challenges. This paper centers round the reactions from the banking and account segment .

6. EVOLUTION OF E-COMMERCE:

7. E-COMMERCE TRENDS-A NEW BUSINESS REVOLUTION IN INDIA:

Web based business may be a blast within the advanced business. It's a change in perspective impacting the 2 advertisers and therefore the clients. Maybe online business is progressively over simply another approach to assist strategic polices .

Purchasing merchandise and ventures through web based business permits buyers the opportunity to choose whenever and where to shop and therefore the chance to research the item, the dealer, and a few other accessible choices. Shopping has been reformed through the accessibility of on-line data.

India's internet business showcase is maybe going to contact \$38 billion imprint in 2016, an enormous bounce over the \$23 billion incomes checked by the business in 2015, as indicated by an ASSOCHAM study. Expanding web and versatile infiltration, developing agreeableness of on-line installments and ideal socioeconomics have given the special chance to organizations to accompany with their clients .5 utilize their own printers or they can purchase the structure and

have it imprinted on the commercial center's printer and afterward conveyed.

Internet business patterns – Another business transformation in India: On-line business. It is a change in outlook impacting the 2 advertisers and also the clients. Maybe web based business is increasingly over simply yet one more approach to support the present strategic policies.

8. ADVANTAGES AND DISADVANTAGES OF E-COMMERCE:

There's no uncertainty that the capacity to sell on-line has made numerous organizations practical and gainful . Like all plans of action, web based business has its preferences and drawbacks (Advantages and Disadvantages). It's essential to urge a good handle on the upsides and drawbacks so you'll be able to be educated when selecting on your vital choices.

8.1 ADVANTAGES:

Quicker purchasing and selling system, even as simple to get items. Purchasing/selling 24/7 day in & day out. More reach to clients, there's no hypothetical geographic confinements. Low operational expenses and better nature of administrations. With a touch research, each business can founded repeating installments . No need of physical organization set-ups. Simple to start and oversee a business. Clients can without much of stretch select items from various suppliers without moving around truly.

With on-line business there's no driving around and around while glancing and diving in trusts of finding what you wish.

8.2 DISADVANTAGES:

Anybody, great or then again awful, can without much of a stretch beginning a business. Also, there are some terrible destinations which eat up customers' cash. There's no assurance of item quality. Mechanical disappointments can cause unusual consequences for the all out procedures. As there's least possibility of direct client to organization associations, client unwaveringness is consistently on a check . There are numerous programmers who search for circumstances, and hence web business website, administration, installment portals, all are consistently inclined to assault. When a business has started as e-

commerce, they must be able to make changes to remain compatible.

This factor creates accounting problems for the Indian on-line business companies.

Global e-commerce sales are growing at more than 19% p.a. source:

[\[http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/file:Global_e-commerce_sales.jpg\]](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/file:Global_e-commerce_sales.jpg)

9.OPPORTUNITIESFORECOMMERCE:

Web based business is one in all the foremost energizing spaces for today's worldwide on-line network, and Indian's youthful startup economy is within the interest of private entertainment. In the under 3 long stretches of 2011, Indian investors have as of now put over \$50 million out of seven web based business organizations, a 400 percent expansion over an analogous period simply a year ago, which mirrors the aptitude of web based business industry in India for the up and coming years. By 2024-2025, as figure 3 shows, 58 million rural households are going to be a part of the "Core" potential e-commerce consumers. The study also reveals that "Poor sec" will decrease substantially.

- With 8-10% of web entrance it offers a colossal marketplace for development potential as around 120Mn of the populace is aiming to web .
- Rate of internet penetration is 10.2% according to internet world stats.
- Ascent of discretionary income and white collar class is adding consumer's ability to spend.
- Number of on-lone shoppers in India is on a pointy rise because the market is building; new customers have gotten acquired daily.

- That force will convey into 2016 whenever retailers irrespective of how you look at it catch the versatile chance.
- Irrespective of touchy development lately, internet business despite everything speaks to only about 11.9 percent of retail deals, in spite of the fact that that's up from just 3.5 percent 10 years prior.

10. RESULT:

To make up the rank request of benefits and challenges within the account and banking industry, the medians were registered. The accompanying tables present their rank requests, in light of middle qualities (and the quantity of legitimate responses) for each factor, even as the sign test outcomes (underlining measurable critical contrasts among foreseen and experienced benefits and challenges).

Rank	Benefits	Median	No of cases	Sign T. Sign if.
1	Increased sales	3.5000	22	0.65
2	Business efficiency	3.0000	22	.013
3	Customer Loyalty	3.0000	22	.063
4	Reduced inventories	2.0000	22	.002
5	Improved images	3.0000	21	.727
6	Competitive benefits	3.0000	22	.039

Table 3 Order and Sign Test for Benefits

Indicated that the foremost achieved benefits included increased sales, business efficiency, competitive advantages, improved images, reduced inventories the results of the sign test indicated that 3 benefits that weren't correctly anticipated including business efficiency, reduced inventories and competitive benefits.

To build up whether there were contrasts between benefits, difficulties of e-commerce over the three enterprises with the foremost elevated reaction rate a Kruskal - Wallis tests was performed.

Rank	Challenges	Median	No of cases	Sign T. Sign if.
1	Technology cost	3.0000	24	.180

2	Budget	3.0000	24	.092
3	IT skilled people	3.0000	24	.021
4	Managing change	3.0000	23	.096
5	Customer service	3.0000	24	1.000
6	Integrating front-end EC to back-end system	2.5000	24	.549
7	Security	2.5000	24	.815

Table 4 Order and Sign Test for Challenges

It will be concluded that the foremost frequent challenges encountered in finance/Banking include technology cost, lack of EC knowledge, budget, IT skilled people and customer service.

The aftereffects of the sign test demonstrate that the test of IT gifted individuals was definitely not foreseen. Organizations during this manner foreseen accurately everything except one of the difficulties.

11. DISCUSSION:

To expand the aptitude of internet business, business must understand the benefits and challenges of exchanging electronically. This examination analyzed these components within the Australian Account/Banking industry.

- The many advantages of web based business selection not foreseen by the part are the identical old thing productivity, improved picture, upper hand, expanded mechanization of procedures and expanded business turnover.
- Participating industry correctly estimated the overwhelming majority of challenges of e-commerce that lay ahead. An IT skilled person was, however, one significant challenge that wasn't correctly anticipated.
- The key difficulties recognized for the segment are the expenses of the innovation, the absence of knowledge on on-line business, handling with the change, planning and issues related with connection rear frameworks.
- Associations vary essentially in their tendency to send internet business (EC) advancement. It's necessary to analyze the factors that determine the organizational inclination to deploy EC technologies because

this may help firms design appropriate interventions so as to manage it.

- It clarifies why associations differ in their affinity to send EC advancements, and features the duty of top administration, parts of association culture, qualities of information frameworks experts, and association structure. Generally, the paper gives a structure by which explicit hierarchical drivers of EC sending will be important administrative issues will be attended to.
- As of half-moon, 2015, seven Indian e-commerce companies have managed to achieve billion-dollar valuation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

We are thankful to Assistant Professor Ms. M. Infant Angel Department of Computer Science, Park's College of Arts and Science for motivation and encouragement which helped us to complete this research paper.

12. CONCLUSION:

Today's digital marketing world, e-trade plays an important role in buying behavior of customer. The net based business industry is a pioneer with prominence in electronic business world within the forthcoming a protracted time . The net based business upset has in a very general sense changed the matter of exchange by giving new openings and breaking outskirts with none problem. This examination has distinguished and affirmed the key factors that the fund/banking industry in Australia has shown are significant in augmenting the potential of internet business. The survey results confirm that the identified factors don't seem to be dissimilar across the sectors . Study shows that the respondents has positive disposition toward web based business since they're persuaded of the benefits of internet business all things being equal quick and helpful and it lessens exchange costs.

E-commerce creates new opportunities for business; it also creates new opportunities for industry and factors. It appears that there's tremendous potential for providing e-business companies . But e-commerce

business faces a lot of challenges in flourishing their business.

REFERENCES:

1. Almeida, G. A. A. et al (2007). Promoting E-commerce in developing countries.
2. Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2000, "Business use of Information Technology"
3. Chiu YB, Lin CP, and Tang LL (2005). Gender Differs: Assessing a model online purchase intentions in e-tail service, International journal of service Industry management. 16(5).
4. Cuneyt K, Gautan B (2004). The impacts of quickness, price, payment, risk and Delivery issues on on-line shopping, journal of socio-economics, Vol.33, pp. 241-251
5. Fraser, J., N. Fraser and F. McDonald (2000), "The strategic challenges of Electronic commerce", Supply Chain Management: An international journal 5(1): pp. 7-14
6. Hannon, J. N., 1998, "The business if the Internet", Cambridge USA, Course Technology ITP.
7. Rahul, D., M. Biju and D. Abraham (2001). "Critical constructs for analyzing e-business: investment, user experience and revenue models." Logistics information Management 14(1/2): pp. 137-148.
8. Lee, C.-S. (2001). "An analytical framework for evaluating e-commerce business models and strategies." Internet Research: Electronic Networking Applications and Policy. 11(4): pp. 349-359.
9. India's e-commerce revenue mat touch \$38 bn in 2016; ASSOCHAM, (2016, January 2), - The Indian express. Retrieved from
10. Mitra, Abhijit (2013), "E-Commerce in India- A review" International Journal of marketing, financial services & management research, vol.2, no. 2, pp.126-132
11. Kalakota, R., Oliva, R., Donath, B., 1999, "Move Over, E-commerce", Marketing Management, Chicago, Volume 8, issues 3, pp. 23-32.
12. World trade organization. "E-commerce in developing countries: opportunities and challenges for small and medium-sized enterprises".
13. International journal of marketing, Financial services & Management research: Challenges and opportunities of E-commerce from Dr. S. Hariharaputhiram.
14. Dan, A., Dias, D.M., Kearney, R., Lau, T.C., et al, 2001, "Business-to-business Integration with TPAML and a Business-to-business Protocol Framework", IBM Systems Journal; Armonk, Volume 40, issue 1, pp. 68-90.

15. Journal of Advances in Developmental Research: E-Commerce Challenges and Opportunities from Patel Rikin.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Anthony Albert He is currently studying in B.COM Computer Application, Department of Applied Commerce, Park's College, Tirupur. From the University of Bharathiar, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India. He has published more than 2 research papers in International journal and conference it's also available in online.

Aravinth He is currently studying in B.COM Computer Application, Department of Applied Commerce, Park's College, Tirupur. From the University of Bharathiar, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu, India.